

An extra growing season, a powerful incentive.

This could be the most significant benefit of adding containerised radiata seedlings or cuttings into a plantation programme. Simply by utilising the benefits of out-of-season planting, possible with containerised stock, an extra season of growth per plantation cycle is possible.

How is this so? Harvesting of plantations is nearly an all-year-round operation. Restricting replanting to the May - August period, any land coming available for replanting in the other eight months simply grows weeds until the next planting season comes round. Containerised stock, because it is planted with a fully intact root system, is far better able to withstand handling and planting in months of normally active plant growth. This means that the planting season can be extended.

New Zealand is blessed with an essentially ideal climate for radiata growth, with vast areas having suitable year-round rainfall to allow for almost year-round planting. Of course, not all regions are so blessed, but even droughty sites have many months outside the traditional planting season when containerised stock can be planted.

Nov Dec Jan Feb Mar Apr May Jun Jul Aug Sep Oct Nov Dec
The growth advantage of an extra growing season is readily apparent. The value of this extra season translates to more timber, or an earlier harvest.

What are the benefits of out of season planting with containerised stock? Obviously capturing an extra summer growing season is a major growth advantage. Less obvious gains are a longer planting season for the planting and soil preparation crews, and quite possibly a significantly reduced herbicide requirement too.

Some costs are attached to changing to containerised

stock. Probably the biggest will be staff training,

although this should be minimal as containerised stock is generally easier to handle and plant without damage. Better land preparation may be desired, but then planting, especially with a Pottiputki planting tube, is significantly faster.

The decision is yours.

Radiata pine cuttings for New Zealand plantations in Lannen 63F seedling trays.

Who's planting containerised radiata?

Forenza nursery has probably the biggest containerised radiata cuttings programme in New Zealand, followed by Southern Woods. Both produce the bulk of their stock in Lannen 63F trays, and mostly from cuttings from aged mother plants.

Commercial radiata containerised stock is not yet common, although probably 10 or so nurseries can grow this stock type. In addition, many of these nurseries also grow seedlings of other plantation forestry species in containers.

Obviously there is a degree of commercial sensitivity attached to this. Suffice to say, those who have latched onto using containerised stock have been cautiously increasing their requirements since the 1994 boom years when side slot Lannen seedling trays first appeared in New Zealand nurseries.

The idea of containerised plantation stock is used extensively in many other countries. Chile is probably the country now using containerised radiata stock to the greatest extent. South Africans have many years practical

In Chile, containerised radiata cuttings are already being used extensively for plantation purposes.

experience with using containerised pine seedling stock. While in Australia, a large new nursery to propagate containerised pinaster cuttings has already been operating for a few years.

What's the buzz about side slots anyway?

It is obvious from the seedling trays why they are called side slot trays. But why add such an obvious extra complexity to the moulding process? The answer in a nutshell is lateral root-pruning. What we should really be asking is why root-pruning?

Early container designs used for forestry are still to be found, for example some of the simpler tray designs used for vegetable seedlings. These cells typically have smooth internal walls, and also a base with a drainage hole through it. Easy to make, easy to remove the well-formed root-plugs that develop in them, but an outright disaster for plantation trees as the roots form a twisted knot. The simplest way around this problem is to leave the base of the cell open so roots have nothing to guide them round the bottom, and then to include little ribs running down the cell to ensure roots cannot circle. A number of commercial forestry container systems are still sold where these are the only design features reducing root-form problems.

The Lannen 63F tray, 90mm deep cells, is a popular size for radiata seedlings and cuttings. Sculpted cell walls and air-pruning side slots aid in root development.

Root-pruning of containerised-stock is very similar to that of bare-root nursery methods. In both cases the objective is to produce a fibrous, well-branched root system that will eventually grow into a natural root form.

- A- Air-pruning of the tap root occurs at the base of the container, while undercutting is done in the nursery bed.
- B- Lateral roots are pruned by exposure to air because of the side slots in the container, while special cutting discs are used in the nursery bed.
- C- Root-wrenching or trimming roots on lifting are not required in containerised nursery systems.

Containerised pine seedlings with the roots washed out to show the root system. On the left is a typical root-cage formed when the lateral roots are forced to grow downwards. On the right is a fibrous, branched lateral root system produced by lateral root-pruning.

While these measures were an enormous benefit and allowed the foresters to use the other benefits of containerised stock types to good effect, an occasional problem with tree stability continued. Various research efforts have all come to the same conclusion - the root system must not be shaped by the container. Put another way, the root system after planting must be allowed to develop a natural root form.

How can we prevent the roots from being guided by the walls of the container? Cut them off when they get to the wall. Early methods created some ingenious tray designs to run a blade down to cut the roots, clearly an idea inspired by side-cutting used in open-root nursery beds.

Two other means of pruning the roots can be done. Various chemicals have been tested in their effect of killing the root tip. In practice, copper has found favour in some systems, particularly where expanded polystyrene trays are used. The other method is to dry out the tip - air root-pruning. And this brings us back to the side-slots in the trays. Roots are guided to the slots in the cell wall where the tips are dried in the air, and all the benefits of lateral root-pruning occur.

Melbourne

PO Box 295, BERWICK, Vic 3806
Tel 03-9769 9733 Fax 03-9769 9722

Perth

PO Box 246, Rockingham City, WA 6169
Tel 08-9591 1200 Fax 08-9591 1300

Auckland

PO Box 79-340, Royal Heights
Tel 09-837 4466 Fax 09-837 4468

Growth Points® is published by Transplant Systems Limited, PO Box 29-074, Christchurch. Editor: Warrick Nelson. Views are not necessarily those of Transplant Systems Limited, Transplant Systems Pty Limited, or Lannen Plant Systems, Finland. Duplication and distribution of articles is encouraged providing suitable acknowledgement is made. Whilst every effort is made to ensure accuracy, no liability is accepted for errors of fact or opinion.